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Human Factors in Systems Investigations of Heavy Vehicle Crashes at Level Crossings: Causal or Contributory?

Ivan Cikara^{1*}, Geoff Dell², and Aldo Raineri¹

¹ Central Queensland University

² Central Queensland University and VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Collisions at railway level crossings are the largest cause of Australian rail-related fatalities and are more likely to result in fatalities than other types of road collisions. An Australian Government review of collisions at level crossings found that the behaviour of motor vehicle drivers has consistently been cited as the most significant factor contributing to crashes at level crossings. This is supported by an analysis conducted by the Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB) of collisions at level crossings which identified that the primary factor in almost every collision was the vehicle driver's failure to abide by the traffic control measures at the level crossing.

This study thematically analysed the findings of 17 investigation reports completed by the ATSB of crashes involving heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings. In most instances, the ATSB investigation reports identified heavy vehicle driver behaviour as the cause of the crashes. This analysis outlines the various human factor elements that the ATSB reports suggest contributed to the crashes and, in contrast, notes that these elements are the end result of an investigation that does not appear to go beyond findings and classification of human error to explore why these human errors occurred and contributed to the crash.

This study argues that the attribution of human error should be the beginning of an investigation not the end. While driver error was attributed by the ATSB as the primary cause of most crashes, it should not be considered as the primary cause but rather the outcome of a set of underlying factors and decision-making processes which, combined together, culminate in that error occurring. A number of these factors are influenced by the socio-technical system within which the heavy vehicle driver operates. Focus of effort is needed to investigate and analyse the prevailing circumstances and socio-technical system influences in order to discover the underlying factors leading to the human error.

* *Corresponding author*: ivan.cikara@cqumail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Collisions at level crossings are the largest cause of rail related fatalities in Australia. While they are a relatively rare occurrences, representing approximately 1% of the national annual road toll (Larue et al., 2018b), level crossing crashes are more likely to result in fatalities than other road collisions and level crossing incidents are also more costly, with the estimated conservative cost of a fatality being at 1.9 million dollars (Di Milia et al., 2012). Research of all crashes that occurred at level crossings between 2000-2009 (Independent Transport Safety Regulator, 2011) identified that 50% of fatalities occurred at level crossings that were actively controlled, 25% occurred at passively controlled level crossings and 22% occurred at level crossings with unspecified or unknown controls. Most of these fatalities involved cars, utilities, vans and 4WDs, representing 72% of fatalities. 76% of those killed were male (ATSB, 2008).

The complexity of the socio-technical system within which heavy vehicle drivers are required to work adds to the risk of crashes occurring. Both the rail and heavy vehicle environment operate within separate complex socio-technical systems where humans and technology work together both with constituent parts that interact and are reliant on each other (Klockner & Toft, 2014). The two systems have different regulatory frameworks, infrastructure design and operating principles, procedures and practices. A failure to understand and apply the correct decisions at the right time can lead to a catastrophic outcome.

Level crossing design philosophy is based on the pretext that because of their mass and speed, trains are unable to stop abruptly and may take as much as a kilometre or more to come to a complete stop. So, in the case of active level crossings which are designed to alert road users that a train is approaching, it is the responsibility of the road user to observe the warning when it activates and stop their vehicle prior to the level crossing. However, in the case of some passive level crossings there are permanently fixed warning signs that warn the road user to stop or give way and look for approaching trains before proceeding across the level crossing (Mooren et al., 2015). At these level crossings it is entirely up to the road user to check for trains and ensure that it is safe to cross.

Most studies of level crossing crashes have focused on drivers (Read et al., 2021). There is, however, a distinction between incidents caused by driver error and those caused by the influence of socio-technical systems, both of which involve separate personal accountabilities (Vaughen & Muschara, 2011). For example, where a driver's decision not to stop at a stop sign at a level crossing is identified as the cause of a crash, there is a risk that systemic underlying causes may be missed when driver error is identified. The many factors that influence the driver's decision-making process are largely ignored, especially when information bias and assumptions infect the investigation process and fail to capture the systemic underlying causes. Dell (2015) stated:

Too often, those directly involved in accidents, such as the driver of the vehicle, the pilot of the aircraft or the operator of the machine, are the ones that are blamed (p.xv).

Previous research suggests there is a disregard for the warning systems at level crossings and associated road laws by some motorists, including some heavy vehicle drivers. For example, the Labour Council of New South Wales (2001) postulated that drivers ignored level crossing protocols and Davey et al. (2008) found that heavy vehicle drivers consciously ignore the risks involved, with indifference towards their own safety and that of other road and rail users.

Perrow (1984) found that failures in complex systems are inevitable and the occurrence of crashes with devastating outcomes is unavoidable. Although the rail environment to some degree is predictable, that is, the rail track remains constant and unchanged and the train runs along that track, the risk of a crash occurring at level crossings is out of the train drivers' control. However, the heavy vehicle transport industry is far less predictable as it relies on differing road conditions coupled with organisational and driver perceptions and behaviours, which has the potential to increase the likelihood of a crash occurring. Added to this are the unknown elements of driver behaviours which can be unpredictable and unavoidable, potentially influenced by other factors (Quinlan, 2001; Jones, 2013).

The train driver is reliant on the heavy vehicle driver stopping at the level crossing. Added to this are the pressures for governmental and organisational economies and competing priorities that erode safety systems and processes as a result of factors such as budget constraints, pressures towards cost effectiveness, design flaws, maintenance shortcomings, training and assessment, due diligence to name a few (Moura et al., 2017).

So, a far greater proportion of the responsibility for avoiding level crossing collisions sits with the road safety system and road users, including heavy vehicle drivers, who have the principal responsibility to ensure they comply with the warning systems and road rules related to level crossings to avoid collisions.

In relation to that compliance, evidence suggests that heavy vehicle driver behaviours are influenced by their company systems (Quinlan, 2001; Jones, 2013). For example, schedule pressure can lead to speeding or the failure to take rest breaks and can also influence driver risk-taking behaviours in general and in relation to level crossings (Mooren et al., 2015).

Vaughen and Muschara (2011) suggested that a deeper understanding of the causes of an incident, and ultimately making better and more effective recommendations for corrective action, can be achieved when investigative methodologies remove the emphasis of hindsight bias and push beyond the simple human error root causes (Manuele, 2014). Socio-technical system causes and weaknesses cannot be discovered when investigations stop looking beyond human error (Dell, 2015). There are a multitude of factors that are present long before a driver's journey begins and, in most instances, investigations do not trace back beyond the driver error (Dell, 2019; Cikara et al., 2020a). This omission fails to identify the systemic underlying causal factors of a heavy vehicle crash. Dekker (2006) suggested that human error is the effect or symptom of deeper trouble, with these sources of error being structural, not personal. To understand human error, one must examine the system within which people work. Numerous models and methods of analysing crash causation seek out multifactorial explanations as to why crashes occur (Naweed et al., 2019). Read et al. (2021) argued that collisions at level crossings are caused by both the decisions and actions of the level crossing users as well as the level crossing stakeholders, such as the rail companies, government and safety regulators and concluded that factors across the level crossing system interact to influence risk at level crossings (Read et al., 2017; Read et al., 2021).

A review of level crossing crashes completed by the ATSB (2008) found that 83% of all crashes, including passenger vehicles and heavy vehicles, occurred during daylight hours, excluding dawn and dusk. The ATSB findings identified that for most fatalities the point of impact was the front of the train. The ATSB findings also suggested this was because of drivers not noticing or misjudging the arrival time of an approaching train rather than not noticing a train that is already on the level crossing. Excessive speeds were not considered relevant in collisions with only 7% of all reported crashes involving speed. Unintentional road user error was identified as a major contributing factor in 46% of level crossing crashes compared with 22% of road crashes. In these instances, the driver has not seen

the train, did not see or was unable to heed the warning system or for some reason was unable to avoid the train. Fatigue only accounted for 3% of crashes. Despite the findings in the ATSB report identifying factors why heavy vehicle crashes occur at level crossings this study identified there were 16 reports where driver error was attributed to the cause of the crash.

It has been suggested that the lack of progress on problem solving the reasons why level crossing crashes continue to occur is due to a lack of systems thinking during crash analysis (Salmon et al., 2015). When attempting to understand and improve level crossing safety a systems thinking approach has not been adopted (Read et al., 2013; Salmon et al., 2013b; Salmon et al., 2015). Investigations of level crossing crashes has primarily centred on driver behaviour which focus on components in isolation and does not allow the investigation to extend beyond the proximal causes (Salmon et al., 2015). While driver error has been attributed as the primary cause of most crashes, it should not be considered as the primary cause but rather the outcome of a set of underlying causes and decision-making processes combined together that culminates in that error occurring (Dien, 2007; Debrincat et al., 2013). These underlying causes can arise from any part of the socio-technical system. In most instances, error occurs at the point immediately prior to the crash occurring (Kee, 2016; NOPSEMA, 2020). This requires a detailed analysis to capture the points of failure leading up to the crash.

In the context of crash investigation and analysis, the socio-technical system needs to be considered in its broadest sense. The socio-technical system includes organisations and their systems (such as policies, procedures, design, engineering requirements), government (enforcement activities, audits, compliance activities, assurance and governance, adherence to Australian Standards), clients (meeting contract requirement, service demands and specific deadlines, contractual incentives, non-conformance to contract agreements) and the environment (such as weather conditions, road and rail design, vegetation, flora and fauna), which can all interact and influence the driver to either behave safely or make an error. A number of these factors are influenced and affected by the socio-technical systems. Risks associated with these factors are the responsibility of the business operators, regulatory agencies and government, not just the responsibility of the driver. Organisations must take these risks into account when managing driver's behaviours as do other actors in the socio-technical system. Incidents that occur do so because somewhere in the socio-technical system there was a failure to identify and control a risk. Knowing what those factors are, such as risk perception, inattention blindness, fatigue, for example, helps with identifying the appropriate risk mitigation.

The human factors component is the end result of an investigation that does not appear to have applied a system thinking approach to identify why these human factors contributed to the crash. Human factors are only one element of the equation and should be the place where the investigation commences (Leveson, 2011; Debrincat et al., 2013; Dell, 2015; Doecke, 2020; NOPSEMA, 2020). What is important to consider is how did the actors in the socio-technical system influence driver behaviours that manifest themselves into human factors. For example, why was a driver fatigued?, what contributed to that fatigue? Was fatigue caused by scheduling pressures?, was the driver made to breach their driving hours?, if so why?, how was the drivers fatigue managed by their employer? All these questions point to a deeper level of the socio-technical system rather than sitting on the surface at the driver level.

The factors identified through the analysis reported in this paper focus on driver behaviours. However, the risks associated with these factors must be managed under the laws by the organisations that engage these drivers to undertake driving activities (Heavy Vehicle National Law 2012, Road Traffic (Vehicles) Act 2014 (WA)), thereby ensuring each actor in the socio-technical-system has a part to play to ensure risk is mitigated. For example, organisations must put in place safe systems of work to manage fatigue by ensuring drivers are taking rest breaks, the driving hours are in line with legislated

requirements and drivers are fit for work. This is done through internal audits within the company to ensure compliance. Likewise, regulatory agencies which undertake audits to approve organisational fatigue management systems must audit the fatigue management systems to identify any non-conformance or gaps in compliance and ensure these are addressed by the company before approving the company to operate heavy vehicles. Government must implement laws that ensure the driving hours legislated do not increase the risk of fatigue. Should fatigue be identified as a contributing factor in a crash, each and every part of the system must be examined to identify if there was a failing in that part of the system, why that failing occurred and what caused that failing. The same applies for a driver's fitness to operate a heavy vehicle i.e., whether they are affected by drugs and alcohol, health disorders, mental well-being; their propensity to take risks, such as impatience at level crossings, driving too fast; their familiarity with an area creating complacency; journey management of a particular route, for example, what are the speed limits?, where are the level crossings?, how many level crossings are on the journey?, how long should the journey take?

This study reviews ATSB investigations of crashes involving heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings throughout Australia for the period 2000 to 2019 and looks at the human factors associated with the contributing factors identified in the 17 crash investigation reports completed by the ATSB.

2. LEARNING FROM CRASHES

Learning from crashes is critical in preventing a repeat of another crash and potential fatality. Lukic (2012) defines learning from crashes as a process through which employees and the organisation as a whole seek to understand any negative safety events that have taken place in order to prevent similar future events.

When crashes occur, investigations take place to identify factors leading to the crash (Moura et al., 2016). A systematic investigation and analysis of common causal factors, identified from the investigations conducted, will inform learnings about systemic issues that lead to level crossing crashes. These learnings will in turn inform industry and government decisions to reduce the risk of crashes from occurring. In most instances however, blame is focused on the driver (Newnam & Goode, 2015; Dell, 2015; Newnam et al., 2017; Cikara et al., 2020a; Cikara et al., 2020b).

Learning from crashes applies to both the rail and heavy vehicle transport industries, although information extracted from investigations does not always result in changes that would prevent a future reoccurrence. However, due to complex and dynamic interplay of organisational, social, economic and political factors, learning from crashes and implementing those learnings may be challenging (Rosness et al., 2012), especially when it involves dealing with two differing industries, government regulators and organisations.

An Australian Government House of Representatives Standing Committee on Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development and Local Government (HRC, 2009) reviewed collisions at level crossings between 2004 and 2008 and found that 'the behaviour of motor vehicle drivers has consistently been cited as the most significant factor contributing to crashes at level crossings' (p. 7). A 'Rail Level Crossing Safety Bulletin' issued by the Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB, 2008), that reviewed investigations it conducted between 2006-2007 of collisions at level crossings, identified that the primary factor in almost every collision was the vehicle driver's failure to abide by the traffic control measures at the level crossing although there were many underlying factors leading to the collision.

Baysari et al. (2008) suggested that it is essential the causal factors of level crossing crashes are identified to inform decisions regarding appropriate prevention or mitigation strategies. Toft et al. (2012) and Sochon et al. (2013) suggested that if crash investigations are effective then there should be a decrease in the number of crashes as the underlying causes to these crashes are being identified and mitigation actions implemented. Rasmussen (1997), Perrow (1999), Leveson (2004), Dekker (2011), Toft et al. (2012), Hollnagel (2012) and Sochon et al. (2013) all suggested that systemic understanding of causation is intrinsic to successful prevention.

3. AIM

The aim of this paper is to discuss the driver related factors identified in the analysis of the findings from 17 ATSB investigation reports of collisions involving heavy vehicle and trains at level crossings.

4. DATA SOURCE

Two sources of data were used – the academic literature and research of crashes involving vehicles at level crossings, and data extracted from the ATSB website rail safety investigation reports that are accessible by the public. The ATSB reports were downloaded and reviewed. The search of the ATSB data included full investigation reports as well as shorter succinct reports or bulletins that provided information on crash analysis and findings. The data from the ATSB investigation reports only included the contributing factors, being the primary causes of the incident and other supplementary causes described in the reports as being either ‘other safety factors’ or ‘other factors that increased risk’.

5. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

For the purposes of this study, it is to be noted that there are a number of crashes that occur at level crossings which are not investigated by the ATSB. Some are investigated by other state based or federal government regulatory or investigative agencies. This study only reviewed investigation reports conducted by the ATSB. For example, the ATSB identifies in its ‘Railway Level Crossing Safety Bulletin’ (ATSB, 2008) that between April 2006 and December 2007 the ATSB investigated nine level crossing crashes involving heavy vehicles. In addition to this, state authorities investigated a further three significant crashes involving heavy vehicles and passenger trains. These three crashes are not included in this analysis.

6. METHOD

A literature search was conducted utilising online search engines that included the following databases: EBSCO host, ProQuest, Informit, Scopus, PschyInfo, OVID Medline, Embase, Web of Science TRID and Google Scholar. Searches were also conducted in relevant road safety and regulatory organisation websites associated with heavy vehicle safety. This included organisations that were national and international.

Search terms used included: crashes, level crossings, heavy vehicles, trucks, level crossing safety, level crossing crashes, heavy vehicle safety, coronial investigation of level crossing crashes, transport crashes at level crossings, investigation methods, heavy vehicle fatalities.

Academic literature, article/report was assessed for eligibility against two criteria, namely: (1) publication date must fall between the years 1990 and 2020 and must include (2) reference to the level

crossing crashes. Thematic analysis was conducted to identify themes related to the underlying causes of level crossing crashes between vehicles and trains.

This research included the results from a thematic analysis conducted by the authors of investigations undertaken by the ATSB of crashes involving heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings between 2000 and 2019. The contributing factors that were in each report were collated, analysed and then grouped into themes. The supplementary causes in all reports were also collated, analysed and grouped into themes.

7. LIMITATIONS

A limitation of the study was the data source was confined to the ATSB investigation reports which are publicly available. It is likely these reports have been heavily scrutinised by key stakeholders prior to being released into the public domain, potentially changing the original content of the first drafts. Additionally, differences in the investigative process from 2000-2019 may also produce its own limitations as there may have been changes in practices, approaches, experiences and skill sets over these years.

8. RESULTS

The results of the thematic analysis identified there were 46 specific contributing factors and 76 supplementary causes reported in the investigations. Contributing factors are factors that are considered to be the primary cause or causes of the crash. Supplementary causes are additional causes to the crash which are not considered to be as significant as contributing factors.

The analysis of the 17 ATSB investigation reports found that driver behaviour was a factor in 16 of the crashes (94%). In 15 investigation reports driver familiarity with the area of where the crash occurred was identified. However only five investigations identified familiarity as either a contributing factor or a supplementary cause. There were 12 reports that identified the driver either failed to give way or stop at the level crossing for reasons such as being distracted, unaware or being preoccupied. In nine reports it was found that driver familiarity with the areas potentially created the low expectation of a train or that a train would not be present. Seven reports identified the driver did not drive with due care and attention and in two reports the driver did not drive to the road conditions.

In eight investigation reports the acute angle of the road to the level crossing was identified as a factor and in five investigation reports the design of the cabin of the heavy vehicle was identified as a factor. Five investigation reports identified that vegetation alongside the rail corridor or surrounding the level crossing likely impaired the drivers sighting distance along the rail track. In five investigation reports it was found the level crossing warning signals and level crossing warning markings were not compliant to the Australian Standards.

9. DISCUSSION

Research conducted by Kletz (1993, 2001, 2009, 2012) and Hopkins (2008) found that fatalities re-occurred as a result of the same sorts of incidents. These incidents continued to occur, not because the industry did not know how to prevent them, but rather because industry did not use the knowledge from the past that is available to learn from them (Keltz 2001, 2009, 2012). For those incidents that occur within the socio-technical systems between the rail and heavy vehicle transport industry it is important to identify the causal factors from both systems and learn from these crashes to inform future

mitigation strategies to reduce risk of these crashes occurring (Salmon et al., 2013a). McSween and Moran (2017) argued that action plans must do more than just focus on “at risk” behaviours but rather concentrate attention on foundational root causes such as system failures.

Current research has remained focused on particular road user groups, in particular blaming errors and violations on driver behaviour without taking into consideration the socio-technical system factors such as the environment, design and operational context (Cornelissen et al., 2015). Key aspects of driver behaviour such as driver error, decision-making and situational awareness remain unclear (Salmon et al., 2013b) and the causes of level crossing crashes poorly understood (Lenne et al., 2011). Larue et al. (2018b) argued that risky behaviour at active level crossings is largely deliberate, with most violations being motivated by saving time or road users failing to stop at and deliberately driving through level crossings while lights were flashing. It was suggested that road users were preconditioned by past experience that level crossings would be closed for extended periods, so rather than waiting they breached the warning lights and proceed through the level crossing. This essentially rewarded the road user for their risk-taking behaviour, i.e., not wasting time waiting, arriving at their destination on time. This behaviour repeated over multiple occasions creates complacency and a lack of respect for the risks at the level crossing. Other factors identified by Larue et al. (2018b) that contributed to level crossing crashes included level crossing design and inadequate and inconsistent level crossing warning signage.

Review of the contributing factors and supplementary causes, identified in the cases from the ATSB investigation reports, point to the heavy vehicle driver behaviour as being the cause of the crash. This is supported by other research into crashes involving trains and vehicles where that research found that driver error rather than deliberate violations was primarily responsible for crashes that occurred (Baysari et al., 2008; Caird, 2002; Salmon et al., 2013a; Larue et al., 2018a). This study, as well as the research from other academics (Caird, 2002; HRC, 2009; Laapotti, 2015; Larue et al., 2018a), has identified that the actions, decisions or behaviour of the driver were to blame for the crash occurring. However, research has discovered other underlying causal factors such as obstructed sighting distances due to angles of the road to the level crossing or short sighting distances due to overgrown vegetation along the rail corridor, have also been linked to train crashes (Caird, 2002; Laapotti, 2015; Larue et al., 2018a). This is supported in the analysis of this study where it was found that the angle of the road as well as vegetation along the rail corridor and at the level crossing were factors in a number of crashes.

In addition to these purely instrumental factors outlined in the ATSB investigations reports, a number of significant underlying socio-technical system causes that need to be considered in order to understand the complete aetiology of the crash, as outlined by a number of researchers and as found in this study are discussed below.

Doecke et al. (2020) argued that human factors contribute to most crashes. However, Doecke also found that the system within which drivers operate should be designed to take into account human fallibility and interventions such as road improvements, better journey management planning and improved sighting distances, all of which could mitigate and reduce the risk of a crash rather than blaming the driver.

Research by Di Milia, et al. (2012) identified that:

according to several comprehensive reviews of driver behaviour at level crossings occurrences are generally a result of limited crossing/train visibility, inattention, distraction, lack of knowledge regarding level crossings and misjudgement of train speed or distance. However, a smaller, but unknown proportion of level crossing occurrences are due to deliberate violation of crossing rules (p.15).

While these findings were identified in investigations conducted by the ATSB, both the report by Di Milia et al. (2012) and the ATSB investigations do not extend into the heavy vehicle socio-technical systems within which a heavy vehicle driver operates. Additionally, motorists continue with risky behaviours which are reinforced when they continue with their journey uninterrupted over a level crossing with no negative consequence of a collision. This lack of negative consequence reinforces that risky behaviour (Di Milia et al., 2012). Other considerations that may affect driver behaviour includes visibility. This may be as a consequence of an impairment such as not wearing visual driving aides, obscured visibility from dirty windscreens or due to environmental factors such as road and level crossing design.

A thorough understanding of why human factors contribute to a crash is dependent upon where the human error fits within the chain of events (NOPSEMA, 2020). It should not be acceptable to attribute human error alone to a crash. Focus of effort is needed to investigate and analyse the prevailing circumstances and socio-technical system influences to discover the underlying causes leading up to the human error (Health & Safety Executive (HSE, 2008). Crashes occur because of a combination of causes, and there are a number of factors that influence driver behaviour, such as workplace factors, deficiencies in safety management systems, vehicle design, infrastructure design, lack of government and regulatory interventions and environmental conditions (Quinlan, 2001; Davey et al., 2008; Jones, 2013). In a study of the contribution of human factors to railway accidents in Australia, Baysari et al. (2008) identified that nearly all incidents in their study ‘were associated with at least one organisational influence suggesting that improvements to resource management, organisational climate and organisational processes are critical for Australian accident and incident reduction’ (p. 1750).

9.1 Fatigue

Studies have identified that fatigue is a factor in approximately 3% of railway level crossing collisions (Di Milia et al., 2012). Fatigue can also be a factor in a driver’s perception and attention. It is therefore important, when investigating a crash, to establish the level of fatigue a driver was experiencing prior to a crash occurring as well as identifying the organisational process used to manage fatigue risk. It is a legislated requirement for organisations to manage a driver’s fatigue and must establish systems to do so (Heavy Vehicle [Fatigue Management] National Regulation, 2012; Occupational Safety and Health Regulations, 1996). This may include in vehicle technologies, split system rosters, set rosters avoiding night-time driving and compliance audits. When investigating a crash where fatigue is suspected questions can be asked to establish the level of fatigue risk that may include, how long the driver had been awake, how much sleep the driver had had in the past 72 hours or how many hours has the driver worked in the past week. It is also important for organisations to consider a driver’s lifestyle and any medical conditions where there are personal health factors that could contribute to fatigue such as sleep apnoea. The review of the ATSB investigations identified fatigue as a potential factor in one crash amongst the 17 investigation reports, however the cause and history of that fatigue was not investigated.

9.2 Inattentional blindness

Based on research conducted by Mack and Rock (1998) and Saryazdi et al. (2019), inattentional blindness is defined as being ‘The failure to notice an object or event when attention is directed toward a primary task or target’ (p. np). Saryazdi et al. (2019) argue that it could be particularly challenging for drivers to attend to objects in the environment that are not relevant to the driving task itself, resulting in diminished comprehension of the environment should the driving task become more complex. For example, a driver negotiating a bend, approaching a passive level crossing on an acute

angle, deciphering poor warning signage, changing gears, braking and poor line of sight of the track. This increased cognitive load requires a driver to be specifically focused on a specific task that it increases the risk the focus fails to comprehend immediate risk (Saryazdi et al., 2019).

The analysis of the ATSB investigation reports identified one instance of inattentive blindness and seven instances of inattention, distraction, preoccupation and being unaware as a supplementary cause. An incident investigated by the Office of the Chief Investigator in Victoria where a truck collided into the side of a passenger train killing a number of passengers (Office of the Chief Investigator, 2009; Salmon et al., 2013a) identified two important factors. Drivers reported that in their experience on open roads, their focus narrows, and they believed that they were not fully aware of the entire environment around them. This can cause the 'in-attentive blindness' (blank stare) phenomenon where the driver fails to see an object because attention is not focused on it. In these circumstances, drivers cannot explain why they did not see what was visible due to performing tasks such as operating vehicles. These 'blank stares' can also be caused by low arousal levels where drivers become bored, or they have a low mental load. Their attention wanders and they cease to concentrate on the task at hand (Office of the Chief Investigator, 2009). This was identified in Queensland Coroners Court Coronial Finding of Investigation (QLD 2008/392 & 2008/393, 2016) where the coroner raised the question of why a truck driver did not see the flashing lights at a rail level crossing causing the truck to crash into a train killing two occupants in that train. The coroner stated:

Inattentive blindness is a human information processing phenomenon that emerges in human factor analysis in crash investigations studies. It occurs when a person does not notice an object which is fully visible, but unexpected, because their attention is engaged on another task; in stark contrast to not paying attention. This is a phenomenon that has arisen in other fatal rail crossing collisions (p. 18).

While inattentive blindness is recognised as a risk factor in driving (Saryazdi et al., 2019) and in crashes at level crossings, the ATSB investigation reports did not review organisational safety management systems to identify if inattentive blindness was considered to be a risk factor.

9.3 Situational awareness and unintentional non-compliance

Situational awareness is a critical component of driving and is a concept that drivers and operators in complex socio-technical systems maintain awareness of their environment and what is occurring (Endsley, 1995; Salmon et al., 2013b). It is having knowledge of the driving task at a specific time and place within the socio-technical system, taking into account the interactions and interrelationships between the driver, environment and infrastructure (Salmon et al., 2011). It is an essential element when driving and can lead to unintentional non-compliance. This occurs where drivers, not aware of their environment and circumstances fail to notice or observe what is obvious, such as level crossing warning signals and breach that level crossing warning resulting in a crash (Lenne et al., 2011). Drivers who do not actively pay attention to the system within which they are driving, their environment and surrounding infrastructure may not cognitively comprehend the presence of the warning signals at a level crossing. Research conducted by Salmon et al. (2013b) and the Office of the Chief Investigator (2009) identified poor situational awareness as being a factor implicated in level crossing crashes. While drivers with differing levels of driving experiences have differing levels of situational awareness (Bolstad, 2001), other factors such as stress, pressures and familiarity can also affect a driver's cognitive ability to recognise the risks in the system within which they are driving (Quinlan, 2001; Jones, 2013; Cikara et al., 2020a).

Salmon et al. (2013b) argued that situational awareness is not explored in investigations because investigative methodologies used have limitations that make it difficult to make appropriate assessment. Salmon et al. (2013b) went on to posit further that investigative methodologies used to investigate driver behaviours do not support the description or assessment of situational awareness.

9.4 Risk perception

Lack of risk appreciation occurs where drivers do not understand the risks posed by level crossings and do not consider traversing level crossings as being dangerous. In a study by Davey et al. (2008) it was identified that while heavy vehicle drivers generally displayed a high level of knowledge regarding level crossing compliance, they acknowledged heavy vehicle drivers frequently infringed level crossing laws. The heavy vehicle drivers cited a number of factors for this non-compliance that affected their risk perceptions. A unanimous complaint was that level crossings were not designed to be user friendly with heavy vehicles, where, in rural areas particularly, design faults and location choice caused difficulties with sighting distances and train visibility. Another complaint was that there were inadequate warnings of approaching crossings. The combination of these factors of deficient design and protection systems were cited as being responsible for a majority of unsafe driver behaviours (Davey et al., 2008).

9.5 Familiarity, complacency and expectation

The analysis of the ATSB investigation reports identified that familiarity was evident in 15 of the crashes. In nine reports it was identified that familiarity, along with the low expectation of encountering a train or that a train would not be present, was identified as a factor.

Risks arise with familiarity where this factor is associated with violations and crashes. An analysis of fatal crashes at level crossings in Victoria (Di Milia et al., 2012) found that 85% of the fatalities occurred within one mile of the home address. Di Milia et al. (2012) identified that drivers who use level crossings regularly develop expectations about train frequencies and the likelihood of encountering the train. When drivers do not encounter trains on repeated occasions, they then develop a low expectation of encountering a train at that level crossing. This then leads to complacency and reduction in attention and poor scanning. Additionally, local drivers may come to know train timetables for their area and build a mental picture of when to expect a train accordingly and as such their alertness is commensurate with the times consistent with their mental timetable. The report concluded that 'greater familiarity with level crossings can reduce perception of risk and encourage drivers to engage in greater risk-taking behaviour' (p.18). This is supported in research conducted by Beanland et al. (2017) who suggested that drivers become complacent when they know trains are rare.

Davey et al. (2008) identified that due to the heavy vehicle driving task, heavy vehicle drivers who constantly travel the same routes with high frequency become conditioned to the environment within which they are operating. This constant exposure coupled with low frequency of level crossing encounters with trains can create for the heavy vehicle driver the perception and conditioned learning that encourages complacency and creates the mistaken belief that trains would not be encountered. This constant exposure at the same level crossing develops a learned and reinforced complacency that manifests itself into poor driving behaviours.

In a study conducted by Beanland et al. (2017) it was suggested that past knowledge and experience guides the way we seek, explore and analyse information from within our environment that informs and influences our understanding of circumstances and situations. It has been argued that this reinforcement process delivers outcomes where the wrong decisions and subsequent actions can be a consequence of those past experiences. Simply put, a heavy vehicle driver who travels through a level crossing on

multiple occasions without encountering a train will have that experience reinforced and consequently form the expectation that they will not encounter a train. Their vigilance levels then become diminished, and drivers then neglect to scan for approaching trains or make decisions that lead to them failing to stop at the level crossing.

Other trained behaviours that increase risk include drivers who rarely encounter trains at level crossings with low volumes then have the perception that they will experience few trains at other level crossings. This was raised in Coronial Findings of Investigation (QLD 2008/392 & 2008/393) of a fatal crash involving a heavy vehicle and train where the coroner noted that 'there is also the prospect that the truck driver's attention was affected by the low expectancy of encountering a train at the crossing and limited confidence in the significance of the lights given his experience a few kilometres earlier' (p.18).

9.6 Misjudgement of train speed and distance

The research found that it was incredibly difficult to judge the speed and distance of approaching trains and the time it takes for trains to arrive at level crossings. It was found that road users are likely to base the speed of trains on their experience with cars which in most cases are travelling slower than trains even though they may appear to be travelling faster. Research suggests that larger objects are perceived as moving more slower than smaller objects when in fact they are travelling at the same speed (Di Milia et al., 2012).

9.7 Non-compliance, deliberate risk-taking behaviour

While driver non-compliance with level crossing controls is a factor that contributes to level crossing crashes (Salmon et al., 2013b), it is important to establish why drivers are noncompliant rather than stopping an investigation process once blame has been identified. In some instances what seems to be driver non-compliance can be a consequence of unintentional noncompliance; for example, a driver failing to detect or comprehend the meaning of warning signals and inadvertently entering into a level crossing at the same time a train is approaching (Lenne et al., 2011). Salmon et al. (2013b) argues that a lack of situational awareness is more than likely 'at the root' of unintentional non-compliance by drivers at level crossings' (p. 196). The cognitive failure to be aware of the driving environment can be attributed to a number of factors including driver experience (Salmon et al., 2013b) and how drivers respond in particular environments.

On the other hand, there are those road users who, despite every effort to promote safe driving behaviours, experience frustration and impatience when required to stop at level crossings. There are also those drivers who deliberately accept and take risks as they believe the benefit for violating the level crossing controls will save time. It was identified that violations increased when the time between the activation of the warning signals and the train arrival was between 20-30 seconds (Di Milia et al., 2012). Impatience occurs when road users are in a hurry. It was found that there was a greater rate of violation occurring in the morning rush hour. The review of the ATSB investigation reports identified that drivers made deliberate decisions not to stop at the level crossings. When operating a heavy vehicle there are increased time frames to recommence acceleration and gain speed especially when loaded. It is probably why in one report it was found the driver was undertaking a rolling stop rather than completely stopping at the level crossing.

Davey et al. (2008) recognised that willful violations played a significant part in driver behaviours, this being a wilful disregard of level crossing and road rules. However, what was also identified were the influences that facilitated or contributed to that behaviour. It was identified that wilful disregard for the rules may have been brought about as a result of other influencing factors that encouraged risk taking. What was most prominent in influencing unsafe driver behaviour at level crossings was a desire to

avoid delay in drivers getting to their destination caused by time delays stopping and waiting for a train to pass as well as the requirements to decelerate and accelerate. This was interconnected with time and scheduling pressures for drivers to meet tight deadlines imposed by their organisations that did not factor in potential time lost waiting at level crossings (Davey et al., 2008). Heavy vehicle drivers cited unrealistically rigid scheduling and punitive measures for noncompliance as primary motivating factors for risk taking. Such practices in the heavy vehicle transport industry have been identified as being instrumental in driver violations (Arboleda et al., 2003).

9.8 Driver lack of knowledge of the rules for level crossings

Another key point to consider is the driver's lack of knowledge of the rules for level crossings. Di Milia et al. (2012) identified that there is evidence that many drivers do not understand the road rules that apply to level crossings, particularly those rules that apply to passive level crossings. In research conducted by Rudin-Brown et al. (2010, 2014) it was identified that drivers' understanding and interpretation of the correct behaviour when encountering level crossing controls in a variety of states of activation are quite varied. For example, driver compliance at passively controlled level crossings was unexpectedly low. This is supported by Beanland et al. (2017) who suggested that, where drivers who are relatively unfamiliar with passive level crossing controls, may experience difficulty or confusion when negotiating that level crossing. This may be because they may be more familiar with an active level crossing and be searching for flashing warning signals to assist with their decision-making process.

9.9 Sighting distance and increased risk to heavy vehicle drivers

Australian Standard AS1742.7-2007 requires the sighting distance at a level crossing to be calculated based on the track speed for that section of track. It also takes into account the maximum viewing angle for the driver to be no greater than 110 degrees calculated based on the angle of the road to the railway track.

There were eight investigation reports that identified the acute angle of the road as a contributing factor to the crash, five identified the design of the cabin of the heavy vehicle as a factor and five investigation reports identified that vegetation alongside the rail corridor or surroundings of the level crossing likely impaired the drivers sighting distance along the rail track. The analysis also established there were 12 reports that identified the driver either failed to give way or stop at the level crossing for reasons such as being distracted, unaware or being preoccupied. In nine reports it was found that driver familiarity with the areas potentially created the low expectation of a train or that a train would not be present. The findings and contributing factors present questions. Did the familiarity of the area increase the driver's tolerance to risk or did the driver consider the risk of stopping and accelerating across a level crossing to be a greater risk instead of driving straight through?

This risk of stopping and accelerating from a stationary position was considered by the ATSB (2007) which found that in one crash the level crossing sighting distance was probably inadequate for a 53 .5-metre-long road train to clear the level crossing safely from a stationary start. The ATSB (2007) report concluded other level crossings controlled by stop signs may be similarly deficient and more was needed to assess the risk.

Di Milia et al. (2012) argued that should heavy vehicle drivers stop at level crossings their safety may be compromised because a heavy vehicle takes a long time to accelerate from the stationary position, travel over and clear the tracks. The time needed to do so is dependent on sighting distance, track speed, weight of the heavy vehicle, road conditions and other systems factors. Di Milia et al. (2012) stated that if the sighting distance is limited or insufficient a previously unseen train can potentially

reach the level crossing before the heavy vehicle has crossed, even when a driver has done everything correctly. In support, Beanland et al. (2017) argued ‘stopping completely may be problematic for some vehicles, such as heavy vehicles, which lose momentum and require considerable time to regain speed and clear the level crossing’ (p. 217). Larue et al. (2018a) also suggested that heavy vehicles face extended risks at level crossings due to their longer configurations and reduced acceleration capabilities and that these factors need to be considered for heavy vehicle drivers when crossing passive level crossings.

This factor may be an explanation why, in some instances, drivers did not stop or give way at the level crossing, rather than it being a case of inattention, distraction, being unaware or being distracted. It may not be a simple case of it being driver error or a deliberate violation. Consideration should be given to the notion that the drivers behaviour could be based on a calculated risk. It could be possible the driver has considered the lesser of two evils. That is, the risks of stopping, based on past experience taking into account, the lack of sighting distances, the acute angle of the road, the track speed, the vegetation obstructing the sighting distance, the design of truck cabin, gradient of the road, gravel or bitumen surface, wet or dry conditions, all of which significantly affect heavy vehicle acceleration performance and have all played a part in the driver determining the risk of driving through a level crossing without stopping was, in their mind, less risk than having to stop and accelerate. Even if they do not see a train the historical data suggests an unsighted train may still impact with the heavy vehicle as it traverses the crossing (Di Milia et al., 2012). In a study completed by Davey et al. (2008) it was found there was consensus amongst heavy vehicle drivers as well as train drivers who agreed that factors such as impeded acceleration, size of trucks, lines of sight and angles of approach introduced a danger at level crossings over and above driver behaviour.

10. CONCLUSION

In order to identify common links as well as themes, this study reviewed 17 investigation reports into heavy vehicle crashes with trains at level crossings. This review focused on the contributing factors and supplementary causes and identified human factors associated with heavy vehicle driver behaviour as the causes of the crashes.

This study argues that findings that identify driver error should not be the end of an investigation but rather the beginning. While driver error was attributed as being the primary cause of most crashes in the Australian Transport Safety Bureau investigations, rather, it should be considered as the outcome of a set of underlying causes and decision-making processes that have combined and culminated in the driver error occurring. Driver error is influenced by multiple factors within the socio-technical system in which the heavy vehicle driver operates.

Investigations need to focus on analysing the socio-technical system in order to identify what has influenced heavy vehicle driver behaviour. This will require a systematic investigation methodology that examines all parts of the socio technical system, tracing back to where the sequence of events had commenced and ultimately resulting in a crash.

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AUTHORS

Ivan CIKARA is a PhD Candidate at Central Queensland University completing his PhD on heavy vehicle fatal crash investigations titled 'Systemic investigations are needed to improve safety in the heavy vehicle transport industry'. Ivan has over 30 years' experience working in both the Government and private sectors. This includes working in Policing where the main focus of his duties was on fatal crash investigations, before progressing to the Homicide Squad as a Senior Detective. Ivan's career continued into investigations management in the medical and health industry as well as safety and investigations management in the transport, maritime, rail, mining and oil and gas sectors, holding a number of senior executive roles.

Dr. Geoff DELL is a Professor at Ostrava University and Adjunct Professor at Central Queensland University. Dr Dell was also the former Head of Safety Science Courses. He is a career Safety Scientist with 40 years of senior safety management roles in aviation, rail and other industries. Dr Dell was National President of the Safety Institute of Australia for 9 years and the Independent Safety Adviser and Member of the Board of Directors of Cobham Aviation Services, the third largest airline in Australia, and was the independent Chairman of the Board Safety Sub-committee of Nauru Airlines for 2 years. In 2010, he joined CQUniversity to develop and implement the world first tertiary education courses in accident investigation including the unique Bachelor of Accident Forensics and the Master of Accident Investigation.

Dr. Aldo RAINERI is currently the Head of Courses – Safety Science, CQ University Brisbane. In December 2011 Dr Raineri retired as the Director of Work Health & Safety Policy & Legislation, after having spent over 20 years in various management and safety roles with the Queensland Government. During that time, Dr Raineri was involved in every major strategic and operational government safety initiative, including the national development of harmonised work health and safety laws and their implementation in Queensland. Dr Raineri has also been a sessional lecturer, tutor, course developer, educational administrator and project supervisor in the TAFE system and at a number of Universities in Australia for the past 30 years.

